

Management

SUBSCRIBERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS MOBILE COMMUNICATION SERVICE PROBLEMS IN TUTICORIN DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

Increasing competition in mobile service sector has led the providers to realizing the need to focus on decrease the service problems to avoid the switching over to the competitors. Consumers play an important role in choosing a mobile service provider. This paper presents impact of service problems on subscribers' satisfaction in Tuticorin Dist.

Keywords:

Service, Problems, Mobile, Communication & Satisfaction.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In India, We are very backward in having and using latest technology in our service sector. Due to poor infrastructure, it is not possible to provide quality service to the users. In the day-to-day service activities, some problems may come. Service problems have become an important research topic in view of its significant impact in satisfaction and retention of the subscribers. These days service sector is increasing day by day like mushroom. Therefore, having problems in service is considered very dangerous to the business. As such, service problem has become a very important issue in marketing, it has received much attention. On the basis of service problems, the success and survival of the service sector will be decided.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the factors determining satisfaction of the subscribers.
- To study the subscribers' attitude towards services.
- To identify the problems faced by the subscribers.
- To offer suggestions to overcome the problems.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Error is possible in everywhere. Nothing is perfect at 100 per cent level. Likewise, in every service sector, there will be some problems available. They may be avoidable or unavoidable problems. But in some cases, there may be always some problems repeatedly occurring. They may create irritation and tension towards the service providers. In mobile communication these problems may occur frequently i.e. improper signal, call drop out, signal engaged and so on. Because of that, some time, the subscriber may get dissatisfaction and disappointment. Thus, they slowly switch over from one provider to another provider. These days, switching over are easy thing. If subscribers do not want to continue, at the moment they will change the service provider. So the operator has to concentrate the behaviour of the subscribers. If not, the operator has to shut down their door. Therefore, it is must to study about the problem impact the satisfaction of the subscribers. In this paper the researcher find out the problem faced by the subscribers in mobile service communication.

4. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scope of the study is confined with problems occurring in mobile communication service with special reference to Tuticorin District. In Tuticorin District is known for business and development of multinational trade. So, there are good numbers of mobile subscribers in both urban and rural areas, using communication equipment. Both the government and private service providers have been studied in this study. Further, the study is confined to factors that influence the subscribers to select a particular service operator and the subscribers' attitudes towards mobile service provider. As regards subscribers' attitude towards service problems, the study is confined to the problems that are faced by them in availing mobile communication services.

5. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

PROBLEMS INFLUENCING SATISFACTION

The mobile communication plays a vital role in the day to day activities of every human being who has a mobile phone. Even though, it renders various services to the subscribers, still mobile communication is not fully satisfied the subscribers. While, using mobile communication services the subscribers are facing certain problems. Hence, the problems faced by the respondents are given below

Table 1: Problems influencing satisfaction

Problems		N	R	S	F	A	Total	
Connectivity/ Engaged problem	Public sector	Count	20	34	39	6	5	104
		% within	19.2	32.7	37.5	5.8	4.8	100
	Private sector	Count	80	196	256	83	7	622
		% within	12.9	31.5	41.2	13.3	1.1	100

Disturbance of Promotional Calls & SMS	Public sector	Count	70	21	10	3	0	104
		% within	67.3	20.2	9.6	2.9	0	100
	Private sector	Count	90	109	277	112	34	622
		% within	14.5	17.5	44.5	18	5.5	100
Charging/offering service without intimation	Public sector	Count	39	45	20	0	0	104
		% within	37.5	43.3	19.2	0	0	100
	Private sector	Count	262	167	154	9	30	622
		% within	42.1	26.8	24.8	1.4	4.9	100

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table shows that

Connectivity/Engaged problem: In the public sector, 37.5 per cent of the respondents sometimes face connectivity, and engaged problem, 32.7 per cent of the respondents rarely face connectivity, and engaged problem, 19.2 per cent of the respondents never face always connectivity and engaged problem, 5.8 per cent of the respondents frequently face connectivity and engaged problem and 4.8 per cent of the respondents face always connectivity and engaged problem. In the private sector, 41.2 per cent of the respondents sometimes face connectivity, and engaged problem, 31.5 per cent of the respondents rarely face connectivity, and engaged problem, 13.3 per cent of the respondents frequently face connectivity, and engaged problem, 12.9 per cent of the respondents never face connectivity and engaged problem and 1.1 per cent of the respondents are always facing connectivity and engaged problem.

It is inferred that in public sector 37.5 per cent and in the private sector 41.2 per cent respondents sometime face connectivity problem respectively.

Disturbance of Promotional calls & SMS: In the public sector, 67.3 per cent of the respondents never disturbed by promotional calls, 20.2 percent of the respondents rarely disturbed by promotional calls, 9.6 percent of the respondents sometimes disturbed by promotional calls and 2.9 percent of the respondents frequently disturbed by promotional calls. In the private sector, 44.5 per cent of the respondents sometimes disturbed by promotional calls, 18 percent of the respondents frequently disturbed by promotional calls, 17.5 percent of the respondents rarely disturbed by promotional calls, 14.5 percent of the respondents never disturbed by promotional calls and 5.5 percent of the respondents are always disturbed by promotional calls.

It is inferred that in public sector 67.3 per cent respondents never disturbed by promotional calls and in the private sector 44.5 per cent respondents sometimes disturbed by promotional calls.

Charging / Offering without intimation: In the public sector, 43.3 of the respondents never face the problem that charging/offering services without intimation, 37.5 of the respondents rarely face the problem that charging/offering services without intimation. 19.2 of the respondents sometimes face the problem that charging/offering services without intimation. In private sector, 42.1 of the respondents rarely face the problem charging/offering services without

intimacy, 26.8 of the respondents never that charging/offering services without intimacy, 24.8 of the respondents sometimes face the problem that charging/offering services without intimacy, 4.9 of the respondents frequently face the problem that charging/offering services without intimacy and 1.4 per cent of the respondents always face the problem that charging/offering services without intimacy.

It is inferred that in public sector 43.3 of the respondents never face the problem that charging/offering services without intimacy whereas in private sector 42.1 of the respondents rarely face the problem charging/offering services without intimacy.

PROBLEMS INFLUENCING ON SATISFACTION OF THE RESPONDENTS

Table 2: Problems influencing on satisfaction of the respondents

Problems	Public sector		Private sector	
	Mean Score	Rank	Mean Score	Rank
Connectivity/engaged problem	2.44	I	2.58	II
Promotional Calls/SMSs disturbance	1.48	III	2.82	I
Charging/offering service without informing	1.85	II	2.11	III

Source: Computed Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that in public sector connectivity/engaged problem has the first rank followed by charging/offering service without information and finally promotional calls disturbance whereas in the private sector, promotional calls disturbance has the first rank followed by connectivity/engaged problem and charging/offering service without information.

It is inferred that in public sector connectivity/engaged problem is the major problem, whereas in private sector promotional calls disturbance is the major problem to affect the satisfaction of the respondents.

6. FINDINGS

It is inferred that in public sector 37.5 per cent and in the private sector 41.2 per cent respondents sometime face connectivity problem respectively.

It is inferred that in public sector 67.3 per cent respondents never disturbed by promotional calls and in the private sector 44.5 per cent respondents sometimes disturbed by promotional calls.

It is inferred that in public sector 43.3 of the respondents never face the problem that charging/offering services without intimacy whereas in private sector 42.1 of the respondents rarely face the problem charging/offering services without intimacy.

It is inferred that in public sector connectivity/engaged problem is the major problem, whereas in private sector promotional calls/SMSs disturbance is the major problem to affect the satisfaction of the respondents.

7. CONCLUSION

These days, the subscribers may think that mobile means problems. That much mobile communication has affected by problems and disconnection. If a communication be a successful one, there should be proper and better communication system and equipment's. That's means; it should be an error free one. As communication is the life- blood of the society, the service providers have to concentrate more on these.

8. REFERENCE

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